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A MODERN APPROACH TO TEACHING YOUNG CHILDREN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The organization of early learning of a foreign language for preschoolers in the overwhelming majority of cases is based on the fact that a foreign language is an isolated "subject" that is in no way connected with the general tasks of developing different aspects of a child's personality. This article aims at clarifying different modern approaches of teaching foreign languages to young learners.

Keywords: natural communication, activity approach, preschoolers, integrative approach, construction, drawing, games

Introduction

Is it possible to make teaching preschoolers a foreign language successful by including it in a purposeful meaningful activity, to make the most of the advantages of this age in mastering the language as a means of communication?

For this, it is necessary to study and test new approaches related to the integration of a foreign language into various types of children's activities on the basis of enriching the content of children's activities, giving it a developing and creative character. Such integration should provide the opportunity for children to master a foreign language in constantly changing conditions of communication, the development of communication in the language being studied.

Good results in a foreign language and motivation to learn it are achieved faster if classes include a variety of activities that are typical for preschool children. It is known that the specificity of speech activity is that speech is never an end in itself, but is included in some other types of activity.

These activities provide natural motives for speech. Specialists in the field of foreign language methodology and practicing teachers are constantly looking for sources of communicative situations "motive - goal - conditions", as well as useful exercises for the overall development of the child and fine motor skills of hands. The smaller the child, the more the educational process should be based on his practical actions, because. it is not enough for him just to look and think, he needs to take the object in his hands, determine its shape, the material from which it is made, build something with its help (the activity approach is used).

Methods and literature review.

As we all know, the age of children in preschool education organizations is between 5-7 years old. And it is during this period that they develop rapidly both physically,

mentally and emotionally, and the development of their intellectual potential begins at the first stage. Pre-school educational organizations provide an opportunity for the child to become a healthy and well-rounded person, to develop a passion for learning, to receive regular education 5 days a week, and to learn foreign languages.

It is known that teaching foreign languages in our country has been defined as one of the important tasks since the first years of our independence. Attention to the study and teaching of foreign languages increased especially after the adoption of the decision of the First President Islam Karimov on December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages". In this decision, along with the progress in teaching foreign languages, educational standards, curricula and textbooks do not fully meet the requirements of the times, in particular, the demand for the use of advanced information and media technologies, and education is mainly conducted in modern ways. , shortcomings related to the organization of continuous learning of foreign languages at all stages of the educational system, as well as improvement of teachers' qualifications and provision of modern educational and methodological materials are also indicated.

At this stage, the main neoplasms of a preschooler are the desire to control oneself and one's actions, involuntary memory prevails, so that what is interesting is remembered, and not what needs to be remembered. The leading activity is a game in which they reproduce the labor and social relations characteristic of adults. According to L.S. Vygotsky: "Play is a source of development and creates zone of proximal development. Essentially, the child moves through play activity. Only in this sense can play be called a leading activity, i. determining the development of the child" [Vygotsky 1999: 293].

For this, it is necessary to study and test new approaches related to the integration of a foreign language into various types of children's activities on the basis of enriching the content of children's activities, giving it a developing and creative character. Such integration should provide the opportunity for children to master a foreign language in constantly changing conditions of communication, the development of communication in the language being studied.

To solve this problem, it is advised:

- 1.to analyze the features of the speech behavior of children in the process of constructing in their native language;
- 2.to study the possibilities of building teaching speech communication in a foreign language in the course of this activity;
- 3.to determine the role and place of construction at different stages of language acquisition.

Results and Discussions

Construction can be used at different stages of language acquisition both for the introduction and development of new vocabulary and grammatical constructions, and for consolidating the learned language material, transferring it to situations of natural communication during classes.

For example, the development of new vocabulary on the topic "Vegetables and Fruits" can be carried out in the process of designing children from paper. The logic of the organization of activities dictates the need for the teacher to build simple phrases in the language being studied: Make a pear. Make a big pear. Make a tiny pear. Cut out a pearl. Cut out the yellow pearl. Cut out the green pear. Stick the pearl on.

Children learn to understand the speech of an adult, to highlight key words in phrases, and gradually longer statements consisting of several elements become available to them. The situation itself, gestures, facial expressions, intonation of the teacher help the child understand what is at stake, and if he is mistaken, then the teacher can correct his mistake without switching to his native language: No, not a plum, a pear, make a pear. No, not the yellow pear, cut out the green pear.

Drawing, as well as designing, can be used at different stages of language acquisition both for the introduction and development of new vocabulary and grammatical constructions, and for consolidating the learned language material, transferring it to situations of natural communication during classes.

For the topic "Introduction" or "My body", we create a portrait of our friend. On the sheets are drawn round blanks on which children draw and paint the face of their friend. You can use the following Let's draw eyes (nose, hair) phrases. Do you like blue? Do you like green? Do you like brown?; the child gives a short answer: "Yes / No". We finish the work: Let's cut.

Coloring in our classes is also very important:

1. Similar tasks from the speech development classes "Color by numbers". To fix different topics, but first of all "Colors", "Score". (Phrases are used: Take blue pencil- Take a blue (green, red) pencil)

2. To the game on the "Farm". Children are given sheets with the image of pets. Discussion - Who do you see in the picture? (I can see ...), what color is the cat, chicken, goose (My cat is red. My goose is gray.). There are no templates, everyone has their own choice of color. The next step is to cut out one animal from the picture and settle it on the farm. (Each child chooses and cuts out any animal of his choice - Let's cut one animal.) Repeat counting Let's count cats?, How many cats?

Small dramatizations in our classes are also a productive and favorite activity for children. It involves creativity and often interaction between parents and children in preparation for the lesson, for example, the competition of readers, which we hold annually. Children choose any poem in FL that they have learned during the year and prepare attributes, costumes, masks, crafts and drawings for it at home because the poem must not only be read, but also shown.

Conclusion

Observations of the speech development of children show that the inclusion of elements of construction, drawing, coloring, dramatizations in foreign language classes leads to a significant increase in the number of the child's own initiative statements in the language being studied. All children in the group want to participate in such an

activity, regardless of their level of language proficiency. Thus, a preliminary conclusion can be made that the integration of a foreign language into the productive activity of children allows you to set the natural motivation for communication in the target language, use the innate language acquisition mechanisms that operate at preschool age and make this process more effective.

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